

CCB/NiO mixture as electrolyte material

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Abstract : The mixture of conducting carbon black (CCB) and nickel oxide (NiO) were prepared by solid solution method. The interfacial impact over controlled NiO was identified by various tools. The electrical analysis was performed to calculate the capacitance, impedance, and conductance. This solid solution exhibit an excellent capacitive property under wide range of frequency. The result also demonstrates that the electrical parameters are not only affecting by controlled NiO but also an external DC bias potential. This property can be useful for the application as one of the best electrolyte material.

Keywords : Conducting carbon black, nickel oxide, solid solution.

Introduction

CCB available in various commercial grades based on particle size, aggregate, shape, porosity and surface¹. Due to the conducting property it has variety of applications in different domains such as electronic components, cables, electrodes, electrode additives. The carbon black has unique combination of physical and chemical properties as high surface-area, high corrosion resistance, good conductivity, high temperature stability, controlled pore structure and compatibility in composite materials².

Noble metal oxide or transition metal oxide, such as V₂O₅, MnO₂, RuO₂, IrO₂ have high capacitance, good electrical conductivity, and chemical stability, which can be suitable for many electronic instrument, good electrode material and many engineering application^{3,4}. NiO has extremely high resistivity and low conductivity, which has been resulted high polarization magnitude, it is the major drawback for implementing for the suitable application^{5,6}. Different techniques have been applied to enhance the conductivity and electrochemical utilization of NiO by diverging it in high conductive and specific area nano materials like graphite, carbon nano tube, carbon black. NiO composed expanded graphite mixture demonstrate an extremely high capacitance of 500 F/g at a current density of 100 mA/g in 6 M KOH solution⁶. NiO/Carbon nano tube composite gives 120 F/g 2 M KOH

solution which shows that the specific capacitance depends on the mass fraction of CNT loading⁷.

In the present work the mechanical mixture of CCB and NiO were prepared by taking different concentration of NiO (5%, 10%, 20%) to study its capacitance, conductance, impedance, at high frequency range in the presence of an external DC bias voltage applied at the range of 0–30 V. The investigation disclose the relation of capacitance and other electrical parameters as a function of NiO loading.

Experimental

NiO used in this study was supplied by B. R. Steel Product Pvt. Ltd., Mumbai. The CCB was supplied by TIMCAL ENSACO 250 G. The CCB/NiO solid mixture has been prepared by taking CCB with controlled 5%, 10%, 20% of NiO and mixing it in a mortar for 1 h to obtain the homogeneous mixture. The prepared final CCB/NiO solid solution samples are denoted as CCB/NiO-5, CCB/NiO-10, CCB/NiO-20. The sample is used for further characterization.

X-Ray diffraction of CCB/NiO solid solution was recorded based on the reference work⁸. For electrical analysis of the CCB/NiO powder mixture were consolidated in the form of cylindrical palette for 13 mm diameter and 2 mm thickness by applying 4 tons of pressure by a Hy-

draulic press. The conducting silver paste was applied on the both sides of the palette to serves as electrode. The electrical characterization of CCB/NiO solid solution was carried out by PSM-1735 analyser. One external DC voltage was applied through a DC power supply⁹. The parallel equivalent circuit model has been chosen for analysing the data.

Results and discussion

The phase composition and structure change of the solid mixture were studied by XRD measurement. Fig. 1 shows the XRD measurement of NiO, CCB, and CCB/NiO solid mixture. The XRD pattern of virgin NiO and virgin CCB has shown in Fig. 1(a) and (b). The XRD pattern of NiO gives three sharp dominant peak at $2\theta = 37.296^\circ$, $2\theta = 43.37^\circ$, $2\theta = 63.786^\circ$ which corresponds to the (111), (200), (220) reflection. The virgin CCB has

and CCB/NiO has been measured. The electrical parameters are tabulated in Table 1. From the tabulated value the specific capacitance of CCB/NiO-5 is 76251 nF at 25 V, 10 KHz which is the highest value with compare to virgin NiO, virgin CCB, CCB/NiO-10 and CCB/NiO-20 at 10 KHz. From Table 1 the conductance of CCB/NiO-5 is 2.75 mho at 5 V, 10 KHz which is higher than CCB/NiO-10, CCB/NiO-20. It can be interpreted as adding 5% NiO to carbon black it can improved the homogeneity of NiO on the surface of carbon black and it provide lots of superficial electro active material. It is clear that CCB plays important role to enhance the conductance of CCB/NiO mixture. The conductance decreases as increasing of NiO loading. Fig. 2 represents the variation of capacitance with DC potential of CCB/NiO mixture at 10 KHz. The trend shows that the specific capacitance becomes uniform with DC potential.

Table 1. Comparative electrical parameter of virgin CCB, NiO and its solid mixture

Parameter	Virgin CCB	Virgin NiO	CCB/NiO-5	CCB/NiO-10	CCB/NiO-20
Capacitance (C_p)	5898.9 nF (30 V, 10 KHz)	5091.7 nF (30 V, 100 Hz)	75251 nF (25 V, 10 KHz)	48879 nF (25 V, 10 KHz)	13276 nF (30 V, 10 KHz)
Impedance (Z)	1,30,400 Ω (25 V, 10 Hz)	1,28,640 Ω (20 V, 10 Hz)	1,28,470 Ω (0 V, 10 Hz)	1,31,840 Ω (0 V, 10 Hz)	1,31,130 Ω (0 V, 10 Hz)
Conductance (G)	2.89 mho (5 V, 10 KHz)	0.0015 mho (0 V, 100 Hz)	2.75 mho (5 V, 10 KHz)	2.35 mho (15 V, 10 KHz)	1.99 mho (30 V, 10 Hz)

two XRD peak at $2\theta = 24.792^\circ$, and $2\theta = 43.0244^\circ$ corresponds to the (002) and (200) reflection. The XRD pattern of the CCB/NiO mixture with different mass ratio are shown in Fig. 1(c), (d), (e). The virgin CCB and virgin NiO peaks are seen at CCB/NiO solid mixture at (002), (111), (200), (220). The size of NiO in CCB/NiO solid mixture can be calculated from XRD peak width and Debye-Scherrer equation¹⁰. The particle size of virgin NiO is 29.86 nm, and the particle size of NiO in solute form is 14.91 nm for CCB/NiO-5, 14.92 nm for CCB/NiO-10, and 17.896 nm for CCB/NiO-20. So the particle size of NiO in CCB/NiO mixture decreases with the loading of NiO. Small size particle gives the large surface area which gives high capacitance.

In the present investigation the specific capacitance, impedance, conductance of virgin CCB and virgin NiO

Fig. 1. XRD of (a) virgin NiO, (b) virgin CCB), (c) CCB/NiO-5, (d) CCB/NiO-10, (e) CCB/NiO-20.

Fig. 2. Specific capacitance (C_p) vs potential (V) graph for (CCB/NiO) composites of (a) (95% + 5%), (b) (90% + 10%), (c) (80% + 20%) at 10 KHz.

Conclusions

The XRD confirm the phase composition and crystal structural of CCB/NiO solid solution. Electrical parameters are analysed by impedance analyzer. CCB/NiO-5 shows high capacitance. Basic changes in capacitance, conductance and impedance of the CCB/NiO solid solute occur due to the loading of NiO. There is no significant changes happen on capacitance at external DC bias. This may be suitable for ideal electrolyte medium.

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